

Supplementary Data 1 — Resolution Tables, Task Inventory, Aggregate Results, and Bundled Dictionaries

Ilya V. Osipov

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Supplement to: *Diacritic Reduction and Restoration in Serbo-Croatian (šišana / dešišavanje) — Research Data and Methods*. **Author:** Ilya V. Osipov. **Companion DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.20688771. **Pinned source:** ioDiacritics commit be745a6 (main, 2026-06-13).

This document is the human-readable companion to the **Tier-1** supplementary artifacts. Full machine-readable files (`results_aggregate.tsv`, `ambiguous_resolution_*.tsv`, `final_inventory.json`, `deshishana_<code>.json`) accompany the deposit and are regenerable from the pinned commit. Raw resolution rows (tens of thousands per variety) are summarized here by schema, statistics, and representative rows rather than dumped in full.

S1.1 File manifest (Tier 1)

File	Content	Form
<code>results_aggregate.tsv</code>	every reported number, one row per evaluation cell	machine-readable TSV
<code>ambiguous_resolution_sr.tsv / _hr.tsv / _bs.tsv</code>	disambiguation rules bald-winner with confidence and policy	machine-readable TSV
<code>final_inventory.json</code>	task inventory: C1/C2/C3 classes, minimal pairs with frequencies	machine-readable JSON
<code>deshishana_sr.json / _hr.json / _bs.json</code>	reverse-index dictionaries (bald → diacritic candidates)	machine-readable JSON

License posture: code and tools MIT; bundled dictionaries are generated artifacts from mixed third-party sources (see S1.5 and the deposit NOTICE / DATA_LICENSE_AUDIT.md).

S1.2 Aggregate results table (`results_aggregate.tsv`)

Schema (one row per evaluation cell): `code · corpus/register · label · n_docs · n_fixable · oov · recall · ci_low · ci_high · edit_precision · resolve(on/off) · seed`. All confidence intervals use a document-level (cluster) bootstrap, $B=2000$, $seed=12345$.

Register × language matrix (resolve OFF; recall %, 95% CI; edit-precision).

	wiki	news	tatoeba
sr (156,931 keys)	84.1 [82.9, 85.3] · 99.8%	82.2 [81.1, 83.3] · 99.4%	86.7 [84.6, 88.7] · 99.9%
hr (156,922)	87.4 [86.2, 88.5] · 100%	89.4 [88.5, 90.3] · 99.9%	86.6 [84.7, 88.5] · 100%
bs (114,092)	86.9 [85.7, 87.9] · 100%	88.0 [87.0, 89.0] · 99.8%	86.0 [83.9, 87.9] · 100%

Resolve lever (OFF→ON), chat / Tatoeba. sr 81.9 [80.4, 83.5] / 86.7 → 91.4 [90.4, 92.5] / 95.2 (+8.5–9.5 pp); hr 80.0 [76.5, 83.3] / 86.6 → 89.5 [86.9, 92.1] / 96.4 (+9.5–9.8 pp); bs 86.0 → 95.2 (+9.2 pp). Edit-precision unchanged.

Named baselines (sr-chat). do-nothing 0.0% / 100.0%; naive most-frequent 85.0 [83.5, 86.4] / 89.5% (381 wrong edits); ours no-resolve 81.9 [80.4, 83.5] / 99.7%; ours +resolve 91.4 [90.4, 92.5] / 99.6%.

Real-error track (SentiComments.SR orig/corr). 2,804 real targets; recall 93.9% [92.9, 94.7], edit-precision 99.9%; resolve OFF 82.8% (+11.1 pp). Document-level on the same gold set (7.20% shaved): B2 99.58% (R 95.9 / P 97.9); B2 + gate 99.30% (R 91.5 / P 98.4); redi 99.78% (R 98.8).

Coverage trajectories. bs-wiki 11k→60.4%, 54k→79.1%, 114k→86.9%; hr-wiki 78k→82.6%, 157k→87.4%.

S1.3 Resolution tables (ambiguous_resolution_*.tsv)

Columns: rank · bald · winner · confidence · policy · numeric_guard · candidates. Policy GO if $\text{conf} = \frac{\text{freq}(\text{accented})}{\sum \text{freq}(\text{candidates})} \geq \theta$ ($\theta = 0.95$), else HOLD; the independent prior is Leipzig wiki/news (decontaminated, not the dictionary source).

Variety	Total keys	GO ($\theta \geq 0.95$)	HOLD	Shipped GO rules
sr	29,682	8,680	21,002	1,396 (trimmed from 5,150; 3,754 never fire over 351,994 sentences)
hr	—	—	—	578
bs	—	—	—	481

Total shipped resolve rules across packs: **2,455**. Representative rows (illustrative, not exhaustive): da → da (GO); sto → što (GO, numeric_guard = YES — held next to a number/measure word, e.g. “100 sto”); ce → će (GO); vas → vas (HOLD, conf ≈ 0.86). Full rows are in the TSVs.

S1.4 Task inventory (final_inventory.json)

Case-aware, common lexicon. Common forms **2,355,050** + proper-only **851,071**.

Class	Count	Share of types
C1 invariant (no diacritic possible)	1,421,138	59.8%
C2 deterministic (single candidate)	923,635	38.9%
C3 ambiguous	29,682	1.25%

Token-weighted, the ambiguous class is **9.1%** (news) to **14.0%** (subtitles) — about 87–91% of tokens resolve with one lookup, no context. Dictionary + unigram ceiling: **0.4934% word error**; the residual is concentrated — **50% of the error mass is in 13 forms, 90% in 397**. Segmentation traps: literal dj in 10,214 forms vs đ in 73,973; literal dz in 1,890 vs dž in 26,972.

Top true minimal pairs (error = lost mass of the non-modal reading).

bald	error mass	candidates (frequency)
reci	195,914	reći 209,582 · reci 162,300 · reči 33,614
nas	88,679	nas 399,098 · naš 88,679
vas	87,674	vas 545,500 · vaš 87,674
sto	79,637	što 1,775,707 · sto 79,637
ce / će	56,769	će 847,670 · ce 56,769
gospodo	41,420	gospođo 43,521 · gospodo 41,420
ista	16,876	ista 16,991 · išta 16,876
vise	16,812	više 462,469 · vise 16,812
znaci	14,945	znači 205,163 · znaci 14,945
zao	11,651	žao 200,759 · zao 11,651

S1.5 Bundled reverse-index dictionaries (deshishana_<code>.json)

Pack	Shipped keys	Build provenance
sr	156,931	curated diacritic word list (srWaC frequencies) + injected bald homographs + ekavica protect-list
hr	156,922	OpenSubtitles frequency list filtered through clean Hunspell hr; built to 171,938 then frequency-trimmed
bs	114,092	grown 11,350 → 114,092 via full bs frequency list + hr-Hunspell filter
Total	427,945	

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